

Third Space Perception And Cultural Hybridization In Jhumpa Lahiri's *The Namesake*

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Abstract

Diaspora studies deals with the changing patterns in human psychology due to the shift in geographical location, migration, change in culture and ethnicity. The diasporic women writers expose their experiences of dislocation through their narratives.. Jhumpa Lahiri, an Indian immigrant from West Bengal deals with the lives of Indian immigrants in America. Her first novel *The Namesake* portrays the first generation immigrant's issues and the difficulties faced by their children in the two conflicting cultures. She presents the complex human mind of the characters, their emotions and behaviours in real life. She depicts the nostalgic life style of the complex urban and their transformation through their life experiences. This paper attempts to focus on the alienation of the immigrants presented by the writer in the novel *The Namesake* in the third space and their transformation for assimilation in the new land with hybrid identity.

Key words: psychology, migration, dislocation, immigrant, assimilation

Introduction

Jhumpa Lahiri has been born in London to Bengali immigrant parents. She has published the novel *The Namesake* in the year 2003, which portrays her experiences in assimilation to America. She presents the protagonist Gogol Ganguli, the second generation immigrant faces the loss of identity because of his name change while admitting in the school. The author has experienced the same as her name has been changed when she started her school. Her parents have planned to name her Nilanjana or Sudeshna, but her teacher has preferred her pet name Jhumpa as the other names are too long to pronounce. The displacement from the homeland and the home culture makes the diasporic writers to venture their character's alienation, existential restlessness, nostalgia and quest of identity. The writer deals with the hardship of Ganguly parents and their children in their adaption to the American society. Homi k. Bhabha, a literary theorist presents the concept of hybrid identity and third space through the cultural change in the multicultural land. The hybrid identity arises from the relationship between different cultures. The immigrants when they try to assimilate in the new land are unable to follow the culture of their home land and host land, which give rise to new cultural identities. The 'Third space' refers to the in-between space that is formed by the communication of two colliding cultures. Collective memory regarding the homeland arises due to the alienation in the new

country. At third space cultural transformations takes place which enable cultural hybridity, a transcultural form. Homi.K.Bhabha comments in *The Location of Culture*, " These in-between spaces provide the terrain for elaborating strategies of selfhood-singular or communal-that initiate new signs of identity, and innovative sites of collaboration and contestation, in the act of defining the idea of society itself"(2).

Ashima the obedient daughter of her parents is graduated from Calcutta University in English literature. She is brought up in a Bengali traditional family and her parents arrange her marriage with Ashoke, an engineering student doing research at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. She arrives to USA with her husband Ashoke, distantly from her parents. Ashima is homesick and lives alone in their three room apartment missing so many loving ones of the native lands. She feels aloofness in the new land. The immigrants in the third space recall the memories of their homeland. She delivers her first child alone in America. She recalls India where women go to their parent's home and they are taken care for the arrival of the new baby. Vijay Agnew remarks this in *Diaspora Memory and Identity: A Search for Identity*,

The individual living in the diaspora experiences a dynamic tension everyday between 'here' and remembering 'there', between memories of places of origins and entanglements with places of residence, and between the metaphorical and physical home.(19)

Living in Cambridge “She is terrified to raise a child in a country where she is related to no one, where she knows so little, where life seems tentative and spare” (6). She is alienated in the new land without the support of her family members. So when she returns from the hospital she says to her husband, “I don’t want to raise Gogol alone in this country. It’s not right. I want to go back”(35). Her nostalgia makes her to connect with her homeland. The only solace to her was to read *Desh* magazine. “The printed pages of Bengali type, slightly rough the touch, are a perpetual comfort to her” (6). The writer focuses on the cultural dislocation of the immigrants. Traditional values bring people together and they are part of one’s identity. Families give importance to maintain tradition. Ashima also tries to fix in her roots. Her grandmother has not admonished Ashima like her parents or other relatives, “not to eat beef or wear skirts or cut off her hair or forget her family the moment she landed in Boston” (37). She is the only person, who predicts that “Ashima would never change” (37). Ashima is depressed during her initial stay in the foreign land. Ashima is reluctant and feels lonely as her relatives are not with her. She tries to assimilate in the new land and finds a job as librarian and creates contact with the outside world. Her mingling with the American colleagues makes her confident. She realizes: Now that there is no one to feed or entertain or talk to for weeks at a time. At forty- eight she has come to experience the solitude that her husband and son and daughter already know, and which they claim not to mind. “It is not such a big deal,” her children tell her. “Everyone should live on their own at some point.” But Ashima feels too old to learn such a skill. (161) The search for identity is one of the issues of the diasporic people. All the characters in the novel *The Namesake* struggle for identity. Ashima compromises between two different cultures and has ventured an identity which belongs neither to her homeland nor to the host land. Her metamorphosis makes her to create a mixed identity. Iqbal Mahmood in his work *Strategies of Negation: Postcolonial Themes and conflicts in the English Language Literature of the East Indian Diaspora* points out the problem of identity in women:

Uncertainty gives rise to convenient manipulation of portrayals of self-identity, crafted to fit the immediate situations. The temporality of identity in the context of situations self-imposed upon the individual in an attempt to alleviate the feeling of not belonging is a strategy of negation, a strategy of compromise, which allows a new immigrant to the western world to find some degree of acceptance, albeit minimal, a sense of validation, to continue living in a marginalized status. (38)

At the end of the novel Ashima transforms successfully from the difficult situations she faced in her life. She is able to accustom in the hostland even after the death of Ashoke. It is an unacceptable change in her as she is a typical Indian wife willingly dependent on her husband. She even refuses to utter the name of her husband and does not change her dress code of wearing saree. She lives as an Indian woman devoted to her husband and children accepting all the sufferings in her life. Her transformation shows her acceptance of the American life style of both children. Her motherly affection throughout their growing up stage shows her roots fixed in the native culture. Her life is decided with the well beings of her family members. Ashima has learnt everything in her life either by her husband, parents or even children be it driving a car, or celebrating Christmas with all ritualistic fun. “I did not know a thing back then” (285). Finally she decides herself to move to Calcutta for six months and remaining six months with her children in America. Her homelessness is exhibited by the writer, “True to the meaning of her name, she will be without borders, without a home of her own, a resident everywhere and nowhere” (276). Homi.K.Bhabha reflects in *The Location of Culture*, “The borderline works of culture demands an encounter with ‘newness’ that is not part of the continuum of past and present. It creates a sense of the new as an insurgent act of cultural translation” (7). Ashoke , an Indian young man is involved in a train accident in 1961. His meeting with the stranger in the train is short as the man died in the accident within a few hours but the suggestion given to him makes him to continue his studies abroad. “He imagined not only walking, but walking away, as for as he could from the place in which he was born and in which he had nearly died” (20). He

marries Ashima, the Bengali girl and at home he continues to be the traditional Indian male, meticulous about his clothing and food. Ashoke though assimilated in American life also recalls the memories of life in India. His consciousness while Ashima is in hospital giving birth to the child is expressed by the writer, "Although it is Ashima who carries the child, he, too, feels heavy with the thought of life, of his life and the life about to come from it"(21). Ashoke, like his wife, recollects his past in India which plays a vital role as an immigrant. He embraces the fatal train accident and feels, "He was born twice in India, and then a third time in America" (21). Ashoke suggests the name Gogol to his son, in honour of the famous Russian author. He is reading that book while he met the accident, "He remembers the page crumbled tightly in his fingers, the sudden shock of the lantern's glare in his eyes" (18). Homi.K.Bhabha depicts in *The Location of Culture*, "Remembering is never a quite act of introspection or retrospection. It is painful remembering, pulling together of the disembodied past to make sense of the present" (63). The couples try to fix their roots by preparing Indian food, inviting Bengali families for rituals and having friendship with them. At the same time they cook American style of baking chicken or preparing burgers etc. They want to follow the native culture and pass it on to their children. Gogol and Sonia grow in hybrid culture, part Bengali and part American. They often visit Calcutta to have relationship with their relatives sacrificing their comforts in America. Ashima talks to Gogol about the importance of Durga Pooja and also insists him to memorize four lines children's poem by Tagore. At the same time she trains her child to watch 'Sesame Street' and the 'Electric Company' in order to compete with the Americans at school.

The second generation immigrants struggle to create their identity and culture. As they are born in America they try to assimilate in the American culture. But they are not accepted by the Americans. In this novel Gogol, Sonia and Moushimi face the second generation problems in their life. They decide to choose their own career. They act against the wish of their parents. Gogol's parents want him to pursue Engineering degree but he decides to study architecture.

Moushimi's parents wish her to be a chemist but she plans to study French. Sonia studies law. Moushimi hates to marry a Bengali boy according to the wish of her parents. She flirts with her fellow students as an act of vengeance to her parents. She breaks her life with Gogol and maintains her relationship with Dimitri. Sonia decides to marry Ben who is half Chinese and half Jewish.

Gogol struggles with the name given by his father at his birth. At school his parents planned to change the name as Nikhil, but Gogol does not accept the new name. But later his name becomes a problem for Gogol, because he feels he lost the identity with the Russian name. It makes him to detach himself from both the heritage, India and America. Gogol decides to use his legal name, Nikhil, and the name brings him more confidence and independent identity. He practices the western life style as a teenager and falls in love with Maxine, an American. He admires the freedom given to her by her parents. After the death of his father he breaks his relationship with Maxine. He marries Moushimi his childhood friend, a second generation immigrant. She wishes to lead the American life style. Gogol's relationship with Moushimi also ends because she has an affair with Dimitri. He decides to start a new job. The author exposes his agony when his mother plans to spend six month in Calcutta leaving him to lead an independent life., "Without people in the world to call him Gogol, no matter how long he himself lives, Gogol Ganguly will, Once and for all, vanish from lips of loved ones. And so, cease to exist. Yet his eventual demise provides no sense of victory, no solace, it provides no solace at all" (289).

Conclusion

The problem arises in the construction of cultural identity for the settlers in the United States. Ashima's metamorphosis from a nineteen years Bengali girl to a self-dependent woman is clearly portrayed by the writer in the novel. She overcomes all the obstacles in her life and achieves the meaning of her name Ashima, the limitless. Gogol straddles between two cultures India and America. Even though his parents insist the root culture he avoids Indian heritage. He returns to the family after his failure in relationship with Ruth, Maxine and Moushimi. Finally he realizes that he should not abandon one culture for the other and his

identity arises from both the culture, a hybrid identity. Sonia's marriage with Ben is accepted by the family members. Jhumpa Lahiri's novel *The Namesake* explores the third space perception and the creation of hybrid identity of the immigrant characters.

Works Cited

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"Everyone should live on their own at some point, but Ashima feels too old to learn such a skill." (Lahiri, 161). But during the later years of her life, after the death of her husband, she does a similar compromise with the host culture. So Ashima somehow manages to negotiate between two different cultures. "She does the laundry once a month. She no longer dusts, or notices dust, for that matter. She eats on the sofa, in front of the television, simple meals of buttered toast and dal, a single pot lasting her a week and an omelette to go with it if she has energy to bother. Sometimes she eats the way Gogol and Sonia do when they visit, standing in front of the refrigerator, not bothering to heat up the food in the oven or to put it on a plate." (Lahiri, 162)